

ANALYSIS OF THE PERMEABILITY IN RTM REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present paper tries to address the questions of permeability and non-uniform flow at the flow front in RTM. First, Darcy's law as a model for the flow in RTM is critically scrutinized in two different experiments, point injection and unidirectional flow, both of which agree excellently with theory. The experimental results for two different unidirectional fabrics are found to be well described by a theory for the permeability in this type of media. The non-uniform flow at the flow front is analysed with an approximate theory which agrees qualitatively well with experiments. The effective in-plane permeability of a stack of different fabrics is derived from Darcy's law and found to agree reasonably well with experiments. A direct comparison of the permeability of different reinforcements shows that the microgeometry is an important factor for the permeability.

KEYWORDS: Fiber, Flow analysis, Flow front, Micromechanics, Permeability, Resin transfer molding

1. INTRODUCTION

The permeability of fibrous reinforcements is of paramount importance in most composites manufacturing techniques, *e.g.* in resin transfer molding (RTM) which will be discussed in the present paper. Permeability is defined by Darcy's law [1] which predicts a linear relationship between the pressure gradient and the flow velocity. There still seems to be some disagreement in the literature about the validity of Darcy's law with evidence both against [2,3] and in favour of it [4,5,6,7,8]. It is clear from the results in Section 2 that, at least under some circumstances, Darcy's law gives a very good description of the flow in RTM.

In RTM the in-plane permeability is particularly interesting although also the cross-plane permeability may be important in some cases *e.g.* with point-injection through the thickness of the reinforcement stack. The theory and experiments presented in the present paper are concentrated on unidirectional reinforcements which are of great importance in manufacturing of high performance composites.

On a micromechanical level there will be at least two characteristic length scales in a real unidirectional reinforcement, the fibre diameter and the diameter of the fibre bundles out of which the reinforcement is made. The geometry will also exhibit some spatial non-uniformity even if it is made with great care, two examples are shown in Photo 1 which shows Ahlström R12-256 and in Photo 2 which shows Brochier Lyvertex 21130. The question of permeability in an idealized unidirectional reinforcement has been treated theoretically by Gebart [7] who derived expressions for the permeability both for flow along and for flow perpendicular to the fibres. The theory is based on the assumption that the fibres are perfectly distributed in a periodic "array". This is not strictly true for real reinforcements but the theory is still of interest since it captures the anisotropy of the permeability in a qualitatively correct way. It is of

particular interest that the flow will be completely "pinched off" for flow perpendicular to the fibres at a characteristic fibre volume fraction. For higher volume fractions than the characteristic one flow along the fibres will still be possible.

One of the advantages with RTM is the freedom the designer has to choose the laminate characteristics. Typically a laminate consists of several layers with different orientations which may, during the processing phase, result in a permeability different from that in any of the layers. It may often be the case that the permeability along a given spatial direction in different layers differs by several orders of magnitude. This will result in a flow velocity difference between the layers and a non-uniform flow at the flow front. Most of today's mold filling simulation codes ignore this fact and solve for a velocity average through the thickness with boundary conditions that are valid for a "plug flow". Hence, it is of importance to study the flow phenomena at the flow front in some detail and to consider the effect on the boundary conditions as was done by Fracchia [4]. In Section 4 a simplified analysis is presented which seems to agree fairly well with the finite element calculations and the analysis done by Fracchia. The theoretical results are then compared with experiments in the same Section.

Another important question in RTM is whether the permeability some distance away from the flow front can be determined if the permeability of each layer is known. This question is addressed in Section 5.

2. MEASUREMENT OF PERMEABILITY

2.1 General considerations Several techniques for the measurement of permeability can be devised assuming that Darcy's law is a valid description of the flow. The two techniques of most interest for the determination of in-plane permeability of composites reinforcements are probably unidirectional flow into a uniformly thick "beam" mold and radial flow into a uniformly thick "plate" mold. In both cases it is of utmost importance that the temperature is controlled and that the mold is sufficiently stiff to keep the cavity thickness reasonably close to its nominal thickness. In the unidirectional flow experiments it is also very important that any leakage of resin around the reinforcement on any side is prevented.

Typical injection type polyesters have been shown to behave as Newtonian fluids under injection conditions [7] and it seems safe to assume that this is also the case for other low viscosity resins which are common in RTM. However, should the resin exhibit non-Newtonian behaviour it is no longer possible to define the permeability in the same way as we do in the present paper.

All thermosets will exhibit an increasing viscosity when the degree of cure increases (it is still possible to think of the resin as a Newtonian fluid). Hence, it is important that the resin recipe (catalyst-accelerator-inhibitor) is optimized to give sufficiently slow increase of the degree of cure to justify an assumption of constant viscosity during injection. In our experiments we have more than 15 minutes at our disposal from catalyst addition to any significant increase in viscosity [7].

2.1 Experimental procedure and equipment The molds used in our permeability measurements are of either "beam" or "plate" type. In both molds the bottom part of the cavity is made from a slab of 50 mm thick aluminium and the top part is made from transparent PMMA which enables visual observation of the flow front. The top part is not as stiff as the bottom part and has therefore been reinforced with a steel frame so that the measured deflection at 0.1 MPa over-pressure is only a few percent of the cavity thickness (3 mm).

The injection of unsaturated polyester is done at low pressure (typically 0.1 MPa) with a "pressure pot" into the centre of the "plate" mold (where a round hole is cut in the reinforcement) or into the end of the "beam" mold and the pressure in the pressure pot is adjusted to keep the pressure in the mold entrance constant.

In the unidirectional flow experiments the pressure is measured at the beginning of the reinforcement while the flow front position is continuously monitored. Darcy's law can for a one-dimensional flow with moving front and constant boundary pressures be integrated to [7]:

$$x_f^2 = 2 \frac{K_{xx}}{\mu} \frac{\Delta p}{(1 - V_f)} t \quad (1)$$

where x_f is the flow front position at time t measured from the time when resin wets the beginning of the reinforcement at $x_f = 0$ where the pressure is Δp higher than at the flow front at all times. The experimental data are evaluated by a linear fit to x_f^2 versus t from which the

permeability K_{xx} can be computed if the injection pressure Δp , the viscosity μ and the fibre volume fraction V_f are known. Typical results from a unidirectional flow experiment in excellent agreement with the theory are shown in Fig.1.

The radial flow experiments can also be evaluated from an integrated version of Darcy's law [8] which in this case becomes a bit more involved since it is expressed in elliptical coordinates and involves the permeabilities in both principal directions of the reinforcement (a computer program which does the necessary curve fitting is available from the authors). The advantage with radial injection is that the full (in-plane) permeability tensor is obtained in a single experiment. The flow front position along the two principal directions from a typical experiment is shown in Fig.2 where the agreement with the analytical solution (solid lines) is seen to be excellent. The results in Fig. 1 and 2 are representative of all experiments and this means that there is no doubt that Darcy's law is a good approximation for the flow in RTM whenever the resin behaves as a Newtonian fluid and the mold is sufficiently stiff.

2.2 Quantitative test of the unidirectional flow results The results from the unidirectional flow experiments with a continuous random mat (Owens Corning OCF-8610) are compared to those of Fracchia [4] in Fig.3. Fracchia made his experiments in a different type of apparatus where the fluid (Newtonian oil) was pumped in a closed circuit through the reinforcement (no moving front). As can be seen from Fig.3 the results obtained with our unidirectional flow mold are consistent with those in [4] since both datasets seem to represent a continuous variation of permeability with fibre volume fraction without jumps. We believe that this comparison shows that our experimental set-up produces quantitatively correct data for the permeability. However, it must be kept in mind that a considerable scatter in the permeability can be present for many reinforcements due to non-uniformity in surface weight and micro-geometry.

2.3 Quantitative test of the radial flow results Figure 2 shows that the experimental results agree very well with theory but a direct comparison between the unidirectional flow and the radial flow permeabilities shows that the radial flow plate mold indicates less anisotropy and lower permeability in the direction with the highest permeability. The reason for the discrepancy between the two experiments is not clear at this stage and hence only results from the unidirectional flow apparatus, which we think are the more accurate, will be presented below.

3. THEORY FOR THE ANISOTROPIC PERMEABILITY OF A UNIDIRECTIONAL REINFORCEMENT

3.1 Theory for a unidirectional reinforcement with perfect fibre arrangement The permeability in the direction along ($//$) and perpendicular (\perp) to the fibres of an idealized unidirectional reinforcement with geometrically periodic arrangement of the fibres can be written as [7]:

$$K_{//} = \frac{8R^2}{c} \frac{(1 - V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (2)$$

$$K_{\perp} = C_1 \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_{fmax}}{V_f}} - 1 \right)^{5/2} R^2 \quad (3)$$

where the radius of individual fibres is R and where c , C_1 and V_{fmax} are functions of the fibre arrangement. Equation 2 is equal to the well known Kozeny-Carman equation [9] if $8/c$ is replaced by $1/4k$. Equation 3 exhibits a different functional behaviour than eq.2 and it shows, in contrast to eq.2, that the permeability will decrease very rapidly when the fibre volume fraction approaches V_{fmax} which for the idealized fibre arrangements considered in [7] is between $\pi/4$ and $\pi/2\sqrt{3}$. This behaviour is in good agreement with that in real unidirectional reinforcements where the flow is effectively blocked when the fibres are coming in direct contact with each other.

3.2 Comparison with experiments Unidirectional fabrics are made from fibre bundles which are held together by some form of stitching or weft (*cf.* Photographs 1 and 2) in sharp contrast to the idealized fibre arrangement which is assumed in the derivation of eq.2 and 3. However,

the permeability models in eq.2 and 3 may still be used if we assume that they are the result of a homogenization procedure where an assembly of statistically distributed fibres has been considered. The constants c , C_1 , V_{fmax} and R in eq.2 and 3 are then not directly connected to any measurable quantity but have to be determined empirically for every reinforcement. However, only a few experiments (only three if they are made properly) will be needed to compute the parameters which have to be known to compute the permeability at any fibre volume fraction.

The data for two different uni-directional reinforcements (Ahlström R12-256 and Brochier Lyvertex 21130) have been used to obtain a least-square fit from which the constants can be computed (Fig.4 and 5). It is particularly noteworthy in Fig.4 that the Ahlström reinforcement exhibits a very sharp "pinch-off" behaviour for flow perpendicular to the fibres and that eq.3 (the dashed line in Fig.4) captures that "pinch-off" effect very well. The fit of eq.2 to the data for flow along the fibres in Fig.5 is not so good, particularly at low fibre volume fractions. One plausible explanation for the poor fit is that the Brochier reinforcement has an extremely high fibre volume fraction even when uncompacted ($>50\%$) and that as a result of this most of the flow will take place between the layers instead of through them when V_f is less than 0.5.

Notice that the upper solid line in Fig.4 and 5 which represents the fit of eq.2 to the data for flow along the fibres can also be thought of as a fit of the Kozeny-Carman equation to the data. The Kozeny-Carman equation (and eq.2) has only got one independent parameter and this means that the shape of the solid line in Fig.4 and 5 is constant and that a change of the model parameter would only result in a vertical displacement of the solid line. This in its turn means that the Kozeny-Carman equation would give a very poor fit to the permeability to flow across the fibres for the Ahlström reinforcement (*cf.* Fig. 4) while it would give a reasonably good fit for the Brochier reinforcement (*cf.* Fig.5). Thus, it appears that eq.3 is an improvement on the Kozeny-Carman equation for the permeability to flow perpendicular to the fibres since it gives a very good fit for both types of reinforcements.

4. FLOW FRONT PHENOMENA IN HETEROGENEOUS LAMINATES

4.1 Simplified theory for the flow front in a stack of reinforcements of different permeability

The flow in a stack of porous layers with different permeability but the same fibre volume fraction V_f has been studied in the simplest case with unidirectional flow and flow front with velocity U .

Definition sketch

The assumptions is that the stack consists of layers with alternating high (K_1) and low (K_2) permeability and a large difference between the permeabilities. The permeability in the cross-plane direction and in the flow direction is assumed to be equal in each layer. From continuity arguments we see that far away from the flow front the flow must be parallel and a large difference between the velocities in the layers will exist while in a "front layer" at the flow front we must have a flow from the high velocity layers to the low velocity layers. In the theory we are studying average quantities in each layer and the only independent variable is the distance x from the flow front in the high velocity layers. The dependent variables are the pressure p along the centre line in the high velocity layers and the thickness h of the fluid filled part of the low velocity layer. The variables are scaled in the following way:

$$x = s \sqrt{\frac{K_1}{K_2}} x^* \quad h = s h^* \quad p = \frac{\mu(1 - V_f)}{\sqrt{K_1 K_2}} U s p^* \quad (4)$$

where x^* , h^* and p^* are dimensionless. The resulting normalized equations to be solved are:

$$1 + h^* = \frac{dp^*}{dx^*} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dh^*}{dx^*} = \frac{p^*}{h^*} \quad (6)$$

with boundary conditions $h^* = 0$ and $dh^*/dx^* = 1$ at $x^* = 0$. The equations are valid until $h^* = 1$ at x^*_h ($x = l$) which means that the low velocity layer is completely filled with fluid and that parallel flow must take place for $x > l$. Figure 6 shows the numerical solution (fifth order Runge-Kutta) to eq.5 and 6 from which it can be seen that $x^*_h \approx 0.88$ and that $p^* \approx 1.3$ at the end of the slanted front ($x = l$).

Fracchia [4] has taken a slightly different approach in his analytical model for a similar problem. One difference between our model and that in [4] is that we have an isotropic permeability in each layer while Fracchia has assumed an anisotropic permeability with the same cross-flow permeability in all layers. However, it seems that the two models give similar results when the cross flow permeability in [4] is set to K_2 . The present prediction of the front layer thickness l (the value of x where $h = s$) versus the permeability ratio is compared to Fracchia's model and finite element results obtained by Fracchia [4] in Fig.7 where it can be

seen that the front layer thickness l/s is a nearly perfect linear function of $\sqrt{\frac{K_1}{K_2}}$ for all three models and that the present theory predicts front layer thicknesses between that of Fracchia's two models.

The front layer thickness l will in practice be of the order a few mm at the most which can be compared to the typical mold dimensions of several hundred mm. Thus, it seems safe to neglect any non-uniformity in the flow at the flow front in numerical simulations of mold filling.

4.2 Experiments The non-uniform flow at the flow front has been studied in a separate experiment in our "beam" mold. In order to be able to observe the flow at the moving front the stack of different reinforcements have been "turned on its side". We have studied the flow in a reinforcement consisting of two stacks of continuous mat (Vetrotex UNIFILO U-812) beside each other with different number of layers of mat in each stack. The permeability of the continuous mat versus fibre volume fraction is shown in Fig.8 where the solid line is a best fit of the Kozeny-Carman equation (which is the appropriate model for continuous mat) to the data. The difference between the experiment and the conditions assumed in the theoretical model will be negligible as long as wall effects from top and bottom is unimportant for the flow resistance in each layer and as long as the wall effects from the sides are limited so that the sides effectively act as symmetry boundaries.

The shape of the flow front in an experiment with two stacks of 0.18 and 0.47 fibre volume fraction respectively is shown in Photograph 3. The shape of the flow front took its stationary shape a short distance downstream of the beginning of the reinforcement. The front layer thickness from several experiments is plotted in Fig.9 where it can be seen that a linear fit to l/s versus the square root of the permeability ratio agrees well with the data. The slope of the linear fit is, however, less than predicted by any of the models described above (cf. Fig.7). One plausible explanation for the discrepancy between the experiment and the theoretical results is the leakage at the sides in the experiment (cf. Photograph 3) which will result in a smaller l/s than would be the case without leakage.

It is not possible to draw any definite conclusion about the validity of the models from the experimental results due to the experimental imperfections discussed above but it seems likely that the finite element model of Fracchia [4] is a very good model for this type of phenomena and that the present analytical model may serve as a crude model when order of magnitude results are of interest.

5. PERMEABILITY OF STACKS OF DIFFERENT REINFORCEMENTS

5.1 Theory for fully developed flow The laminate in many RTM products consists of several layers of different fibre orientation and in some cases even of different reinforcement type. For this reason it is of interest to compute the effective permeability of the stack from the properties of each layer. Each layer in the laminate is given an index i which is between 1 and N (the total number of layers) with its corresponding thickness t_i , its angle ϕ_i between the material symmetry coordinate system and the global coordinate system and its velocity vector u_k^i . The average velocity through the thickness is then:

$$\langle u_k \rangle = \frac{1}{t_{tot}} \sum_{i=1}^N t_i u_k^i = \frac{1}{t_{tot}} \sum_{i=1}^N t_i \left[\frac{1}{\mu} a_{rk} a_{sl} K_{rs} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_l} \right]^i \quad (7)$$

where a_{rs} are direction cosines defining the transformation between the material symmetry coordinate system in each layer and the global coordinate system and t_{tot} is the total thickness of the laminate. Some distance away from the flow front (*cf.* Section 4) there will be no flow perpendicular to the plane defined by the mold boundaries which in its turn means that the pressure and pressure gradient must be constant through the thickness (an assumption of the opposite leads to contradictions). Hence, it is possible to extract the pressure gradient from the last sum in eq.7. Direct identification in eq.7 now makes it possible to write the average permeability as:

$$\langle K_{kl} \rangle = \frac{1}{t_{tot}} \sum_{i=1}^N t_i [a_{rk} a_{sl} K_{rs}]^i \quad (8)$$

As an example of the use of eq.8 we may consider a laminate of unidirectional reinforcement in an alternating 0° and 90° layup with the 0° layers oriented in the global x-direction. In this particular case the thickness of each layer is equal and the permeability tensor in each layer is diagonal resulting in the isotropic permeability $K_{avg} = 1/2 (K_{0^\circ} + K_{90^\circ})$ for the stack.

5.2 Experimental test According to the theory in Section 5.1 the order in which the layers are stacked is of no importance. In order to test this experimentally a series of experiments with a unidirectional reinforcement (Brochier Lyvertex 21130) was done at about 59% fibre volume fraction. Three different stacking sequences were tested, a pure 0-90 layup with every second layer in the 0° direction and every second in the 90° direction, one lay-up with 2 layers oriented in 0° and 2 oriented in 90° repeatedly and finally one lay-up with 5 layers oriented in 0° and 5 in 90° . The results are shown in Fig.10 where the permeability in the 0° and 90° direction together with the arithmetic mean of the permeabilities have been indicated with horizontal lines. No definite trend with the stacking sequence can be seen in the results, the variations are probably just a result of normal scatter in the data. The permeability for all lay-ups is lower than the theoretical value (the arithmetic mean) for the permeability even though the difference is not substantial.

It is difficult at this stage to explain the differences between the experiments and theory, one possible explanation might be that the interfaces between the layers play a bigger role than has previously been thought to be the case but the definite explanation of the differences has to await more experiments and analysis. However, the theoretical prediction of the permeability of the stack based on the value in each layer is probably sufficiently close to the real value for most practical purposes.

5.3 Importance of micro geometry The importance of the micro geometry for the permeability of a unidirectional reinforcement has been addressed in a simplified analysis by Lundström and Gebart [10]. In this Section a direct experimental comparison is made between three different types of structural reinforcements. The first type is Ahlström R12-256 which consists of parallel fibre bundles which are very loosely bound together by a small amount of fibres perpendicular to the fibre bundles (*cf.* Photo 1), the second type is Brochier Lyvertex

21130 which consist of flattened fibre bundles which are bound together in a very regular way with fibres which contributes about 5% to the total weight of the reinforcement (*cf.* Photo 2). Finally the third type is Brochier Injectex 21091 which is claimed by the manufacturer to give a very high permeability to flow and to be very well suited to RTM. This reinforcement is a so called twill weave with flattened fibre bundles as warp (52%) and twisted round fibre bundles as weft (48%). The round weft opens distinct flow channels along the weft direction which increases the permeability significantly in this direction. Figure 11 shows the permeability at a fibre volume fraction of 59% and it is clear that the Injectex weave has a significantly higher permeability than the other types in the best direction. However, the permeability of Injectex in the warp direction is not much different than for the other two resulting in a stronger anisotropy for this type of reinforcement. For the sake of comparison also the permeability of a 0-90 lay-up of Lyvertex is plotted in Fig.11. The conclusion to be drawn from this comparison exercise is that differences in the micro-geometry can result in a substantial difference in permeability.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The present experimental results together with those in references [4,5,6,7 and 8] show beyond doubt that Darcy's law is an excellent approximation for the flow in RTM (*cf.* Fig.1 and 2).

The theory for the permeability of unidirectional fabrics in [7] (eq.2 and 3) is an improvement on the Kozeny-Carman equation for the permeability of fibrous media since it predicts a more rapid "pinch off" for flow perpendicular to the fibres than for flow along the fibres. This is particularly important for high performance composites for which the fibre volume fraction is close to its maximum (*cf.* Fig.4).

The analysis of the flow front phenomena in a stack of different fabrics with large differences in permeability shows that for most cases of practical interest the front layer will be very thin (a few mm) and that the errors associated with an assumption of "plug flow" will be negligible.

The derived results for the permeability of a stack of different fabrics agree quite well with experiments (*cf.* Fig.10). The discrepancies may be an effect of interfacial effects between layers. However, for practical purposes it seems safe to use eq.8.

The comparison between different high performance reinforcement composites indicates that the microgeometry is important for the permeability. The large differences between different types indicate that improvements are possible.

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Photograph 1: Ahlström R12-256 unidirectional glass fibre reinforcement.

Photograph 2: Brochier Lyvertex 21130 unidirectional glass fibre reinforcement.

Photograph 3: Flow front in an experiment with unidirectional flow into a stack of 3 layers side by side with 8 layers of Vetrotex UNIFILO U-812 continuous mat.

Figure 1: Square of flow front position versus time. The straight line is predicted by Darcy's law

Figure 2: Radial flow front position along the principal directions versus time. The solid lines are predicted by an approximate solution based on Darcy's law from Adams et al. [8].

Figure 3: Permeability of OCF 8610 from two independent experiments. The results marked by ● are from Fracchia 1990 and those marked by ■ are from the present investigation.

Figure 4: Permeability of Ahlström R12-256 unidirectional glass reinforcement. The solid line is a best fit of the theoretical expression for the permeability along the fibres (◆) and the dashed line is a best fit for the theoretical permeability to flow perpendicular to the fibres (■).

Figure 5: Permeability of Brochier Lyvertex 21130 unidirectional glass reinforcement. The solid line is a best fit of the theoretical expression for the permeability along the fibres (◆) and the dashed line is a best fit for the theoretical permeability to flow perpendicular to the fibres (■).

Figure 6: Dimensionless pressure (dash-dotted line) and layer thickness (solid line) at the flow front in a stack of different reinforcements.

Figure 7: Thickness of front boundary layer according to the present analytical theory (dashed line, slope 0.88), Fracchia's theory (dash-dotted line, slope 1.25) and finite element analysis (marked with ■, slope 0.58) [4].

Figure 8: Permeability of the continuous mat (Vetrotex UNIFILO U-812) which was used in the flow front experiments.

Figure 9: Experimental thickness of front boundary layer versus the square root of the ratio of permeability in the two layers. The slope of the solid line fitted to the experimental data is 0.38.

Figure 10: Permeability of a stack of unidirectional reinforcements oriented in 0 and 90 degrees. The abscissa n/N is the ratio of the number of consecutive layers oriented in the same direction and the total number of layers ($n/N = 0.5$ corresponds to 5 layers 0° stacked on top of 5 layers 90°).

Figure 11: Comparison of the permeability of three different unidirectional reinforcements in purely unidirectional layups and one 0-90° layup.

: 0°
 : 90°